

LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES DURING PREGNANCY

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Abstract: This article describes that in the days leading up to birth, babies are extremely sensitive to rhythmic differences between languages. Previous studies have shown that certain sound exposures, such as changes in tone or volume and language changes along the way, change the feeding rhythm of a breastfeeding infant. Ultrasound of the fetus at 6-8 months proved that the unborn child is extremely sensitive to changes and language features. Listening to calm music can drastically affect the ability to learn foreign languages.

Key words: pregnancy, foreign languages, ability, baby, development.

Аннотация: Данная статья описывает то, что дети в течение нескольких дней перед появлением на свет оказываются крайне чувствительны к ритмическим различиям между языками. Предыдущие исследования показали, что при определённом звуковом воздействии, например, изменении тембра или громкости и попутной смене языков, меняется ритм потребления пищи младенцем при грудном вскармливании. УЗИ плода на сроках 6–8 месяцев доказало, что ещё не родившийся ребёнок оказывается крайне чувствителен к изменениям и языковым особенностям. Прослушивание спокойной музыки может кардинальным образом сказаться на способности изучать иностранные языки.

Ключевые слова: беременность, иностранные языки, способность, младенец, развитие.

INTRODUCTION

Scientists have come to the conclusion that the predisposition to learning foreign languages is laid during pregnancy. Specialists scientists from the Department of Linguistics conducted a sensational study that proved that the ability to learn foreign languages can be instilled in a child even before birth. With the help of special technology, scientists were able to look into the structure of hematomas and understand how to deal with them. American doctors and scientists from the University of Pennsylvania were able to develop a three-dimensional diagnostic technology that allows you to study the structure of hematomas and vascular thrombi without surgical intervention¹. The method, based on the use of a powerful electron microscope, allows you to "disassemble" into structural elements any blood clot, be it a hematoma or a thrombus, and understand the reasons for its formation.

METHODS

The joint development, the principle of which is published in the journal Biomedical Optics Express, will reduce the time for examination of patients after strokes or injuries, allowing you to immediately start intensive care.

Newborns are much more prepared to perceive the sounds of their own language than it seems at first glance². According to recent studies, the fetus in the womb is able to pick up certain sounds of its native language. A study by Christina Moon, a professor of psychology at Pacific Lutheran University, found that infants show a marked interest in the vowels of a language that is not their own in the first hours of life.

It has been known for more than 30 years that we begin to distinguish voices in the womb by listening to the sound of her voice," says Ms. Moon. "This is the first study that proved that before we are born, we recognize specific speech sounds in our native language." During the study, a group of scientists led by Ms. Moon studied the behavior of newborns almost immediately after birth, while they remained under observation in the hospital. Two clinics were selected for the study: Madigan Army Medical Center in Tacoma (Washington State) and Astrid Lindgren Children's Hospital

¹ <https://life.ru>

² <https://www.babyblog.ru>

in Stockholm. Babies heard vowel sounds of Swedish or English speech, and researchers could control how many times babies heard vowel sounds by sucking a pacifier connected to a computer.

RESULTS

In the study, the reaction of newborns was tested on two sets of vowel sounds: 17 sounds of the native language and 17 of a foreign language. The interest of children in vowel sounds was studied based on how often they sucked a pacifier. Half of the children listened to the vowel sounds of their native speech, and the other half listened to the sounds of a foreign language. "With each sucking of the pacifier, a vowel sound began to sound, which stopped when the baby stopped sucking the pacifier, and when he started sucking it again, he heard a new vowel sound," says one of the researchers. In both countries, children who listened to the vowel sounds of foreign speech sucked a pacifier more often than those who listened to the sounds of their native speech, and this did not depend on the amount of time since birth³. This allowed scientists to conclude that children learned vowel sounds before they were born.

"These babies have been listening to their mother's voice, and especially vowel sounds, for ten weeks while in the womb. It is the mother who has the first effect on the brain of her child," the researcher explains. "At birth, the baby is undoubtedly ready for something new." This study — unlike others that have considered the intrauterine study of sentences or phrases — is the first aimed at showing the study of small fragments of speech that are not easy to recognize by melody, rhythm or volume. The study examined the behavior of 40 children in a hospital in Tacoma and 40 in Stockholm. The age of the children ranged from 7 to 75 hours.

Scientists chose vowel sounds as more distinct, considering that they can stand out in the mother's speech even with background noises in the womb. The study shows that a newborn is able to learn and remember the simple sounds of his language heard from his mother during the last 10 weeks of pregnancy (sensory and brain mechanisms responsible for hearing are fully formed by the 30th week of pregnancy).

³DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp58-67>.

Discussion: This result amazed the researchers, because previously it was believed that babies are capable of learning from birth, and now it turned out that they start learning even earlier⁴. At the moment of birth, they are no longer "phonetically innocent". Before such studies were conducted, infants were considered a "blank slate". And in addition to the previously existing evidence that babies probably "tune in" to the sounds of their native language, there is now evidence that such "tuning" occurs even before birth. This surprised scientists.

Previous studies have shown that the fetus remembers musical rhythms, and now it turns out that it can learn a language to some extent. In general, babies are the best students on the planet. And although understanding the capabilities of a child's brain is important for science, it is even more important for children themselves. "The fact that children can memorize vowel sounds while still in the womb means that they can make quite complex nerve centers of the brain work even before birth," the researcher explains.

CONCLUSION

As a result, learning foreign languages during pregnancy has a very big impact on the development of the child. 1. While the baby is in the womb, you need to talk to him more often, and you can do it anywhere, at any time, in any situation. The child in the womb hears everything and understands a lot. Often, during a conversation with her unborn child, a woman may notice that the baby responds to her by pushing. 2. Interaction with a child in the womb can be carried out not only by voice, but also by patting, stroking, tapping a woman on her tummy. Such actions also develop communication skills in the baby. 3. To facilitate the process of teaching a foreign language to a small child, you can start training with the baby even when he is in the womb⁵. A pregnant woman can either read foreign literature or start learning a new foreign language. Naturally, the child will not understand the meaning of phrases uttered in a foreign language, but sound impulses that can penetrate deep into the

⁴ <https://lifestyle.kirovchanka.ru>

⁵ Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna. (2022). INFORMATION AND DIGITAL LITERACY: THEIR CONCEPTS AND SKILLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6945140>

human brain will leave a trace in the baby's memory. Children who hear a foreign language from an early age are easier to learn foreign languages at school or kindergarten. 4. But a mother can help her unborn baby not only with early learning of foreign languages, but also with the formation of his excellent musical ear. To do this, it is enough for a pregnant woman to listen to the right music, for example, classical music: Chopin, Tchaikovsky, Mozart. But the works of Brahms are characterized by increased anxiety, so it is better not to listen to them during pregnancy. It is scientifically proven that the notes of the music heard by the baby, touching the nerve cells, are fixed in the right hemisphere of the brain, thereby preparing for their use in the future life of the child. 5. Walking in the fresh air and telling her unborn baby about everything that gets in her way, a pregnant woman also develops a crumb. The more interesting mom will talk about the world around her, the sooner the baby himself will want to see it with his eyes. 6. Mom's peace of mind is very important for the development of an unborn child. In order for the child to be more stress-resistant after his birth, it is necessary to protect the baby from various worries and experiences even before he is born. The expectant mother should rest more, if possible, not meet with people annoying her, forget about all bad habits and exclude watching action movies and horror from the daily program⁶. 7. Every second of his stay in his mother's stomach, the baby gets new impressions. It is they who form him as a person, leaving an indelible imprint on his entire subsequent life.

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⁶ YUGAY E. V. DIGITAL CULTURE AND ITS INFLUENCE ON VALUE ASPECTS OF HUMAN BEING //THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука. – 2021. – №. 12. – С. 422-425.
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